

Future of Performance Management in Artificial Intelligence ERA

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Abstract

Talent resource is considered as a crucial asset for the sustainable development of the collaborative, digitized high performance organisations in this globalized era. Companies are increasingly making an effort to face the challenge of how to make performance management a success within the organisation. Traditionally, performance management system is focused on annual appraisals as the measure of employee's progress. Information technology, big data analytics and artificial intelligence have changed the way management measures employee performance. To achieve competency benchmarks companies have realised the importance of artificial intelligence in performance management system. The quality of employee performance invariably improves due to integration of advanced technologies like machine learning and artificial intelligence that enables the adoption of predictive analytics in accentuating employee performance. The study has significant practical implication on organisational performance management practices, employee performance and employees engagement context in modern organizations through increased productivity, involvement, creation of trust in leadership, supportive management, reduce absenteeism and employee turnover. Digital performance management system will reduce the time, efforts of management and lead to transparency and honesty in employee performance appraisal. The outcome of study is to know the practical applicability of performance management system. The methodology used to study is conceptual research. This study aims to highlight the future of Performance Management system in artificial intelligence era and Performance management methods practiced in modern high performance organisations, posit a conceptual model, and provide a critical view in global enterprise to understand and improve Performance appraisal.

Keywords: Appraisal, Artificial Intelligence, Digital Performance Management, Employees, Motivation, Performance management, Productivity.

Introduction

PM is a continual process designed to identify the ways to achieve organizational goals through constant assessment and feedback leading to improvement of employee performance. The globalized world has intensified competition to such an extent that 'survival of the fittest' has been the norm for existence. Performance centricism

has been the mantra for sustenance and competitive advantage in this challenging scenario. Hence organisations have been striving hard to re-invent strategies and models to measure, manage and accelerate the performance of their employees. These organisations learn, transform and perform developing into high performance organisations. The yearly assessment process, is an on-going appraisal of representatives in a way equipped to coordinate their objectives to the hierarchical objectives. It also makes strong use of goal-setting and metrics to identify progress and areas of individual strengths. Performance management has many benefits that the traditional annual evaluation does not.

PM System in High Performing Systems (HPS)

Performance is plan, screen and audit a worker’s work destinations by large commitment to the organisation. Rather than annual performance review, performance management is the continuous process of setting objectives, assessing progress and providing on-going coaching and feedback to ensure that employees are meeting their objectives and career goals.

In the words of author and eminent HR expert TV Rao (2004), “some of the vital components of Performance Evaluation System are Identification of Key Performance Areas (KPA) and setting objectives, identification of attributes to be shown by all managers irrespective of levels, self – evaluation, performance analysis to identify factors facilitating and hindering performance and taking corrective action, identification of training needs and preparation of development plans, assessment by the reporting officer and sharing the ratings with the appraisee to arrive at mutually agreed rating, performance analysis to help the individuals learn from their seniors and improve the performance, review by the reviewing officer, expansion action by the HRD department and de-linking assessment from performance rewards”

PA Methods Practiced by Companies

Google’s annual evaluation review cycle is comprised of two parts: a “preview”, in the end of the first semester, and a complete review, that happens with the company’s 360-degree feedback collection process. Managers take two main things into account results attained, or what the employee accomplished, and behaviours, or how the employee attained these results. The employee starts with a self-assessment, which is followed by peer-reviews. On the review side, Google employees are asked to review each other, and their direct reports, according to the following criteria such as Googleyness, leadership skills and problem solving

Figure 1: Google’s simplified performance management schedule (1501794944google-performance-reviews-preview_1)

The reason why General Electronics has grabbed the eyeballs of many is because GE is one organization, which had traditionally, swore by the “forced ranking” process and was one of the

pioneers in making it popular in the HR circle. Because GE widely professed this practice, many companies followed suit over the years. The major reason for the elimination of this process is the way it affected the mind of employees. Research has shown that the response that the human brain gives to criticism of any kind is the same type of neural response that they give when confronted with some kind of physical danger. In GE Forced ranking system where managers forced to rank employees. Managers soon developed a habit of giving most employees an average score of 3 (out of 5). This number also decided compensation decisions and promotions of employees. The new PMS at GE developed a mobile app called PD@GE, which enables frequent feedback. Managers are expected to have frequent conversations, named “touchpoints” with their employees, highlighting how far they are from reaching their predefined targets. 250000 to 30000 employees in GE are currently using this app. The most important feature of this app is aiding GE’s cultural change and ensuring continuous conversations. The app and its mobile technology is not as important as the intention behind it to foster conversations and engagement. This revolutionary system of performance management adopted by GE has been in the news for all the reasons and the impact it has on actual motivation levels of employees will be worth documenting.

In IBM annual evaluation system called Personal Business Commitments was followed. Later checkpoints appraised PMS with 5 score lead to balance discussion.

The Recent Statistics of PM

The redesigning of performance management is considered as high priority. Company’s capacity to improve the performance management has improved 10% more compared to 2015. The impacts of new performance practices are high. 90% of companies have redesigned its performance management as there is benefit of 96% its simpler, 83% said the quality of conversations between employees and managers going up.

Figure 1. Performance management: Percentage of respondents rating this trend “important” or “very important”

Figure 2 Performance Management: percentage of respondents rating this trend “importance” or “very important”

Today companies need align goals, proper feedback and coach to provide real time feedback, there is need for continuous learning by the employees and organisations, 91 percent companies have adopted continuous performance management which give better data for decision with major changes by eliminating the bias and discrimination in promotion and career advancement. New performance approach improving discussions, creating frequent check-in and developmental focus. Software leading in a new direction which enabling goal making to be more social, transparent,

mobile and digital. Enabling easy progress tracking by providing continuous feedback, providing instant information, deploying data/analytics, Supporting career development and the integration of PM tools with products like Slack, outlook, Gmail.

Rethinking Employee PM

PM is transforming in the digital workplace to support more frequent, contextual and transparent feedback. HR leaders should explore these new approaches and consider their impacts on related processes and talent management applications.

Many companies, such as GE, the Gap and Adobe Systems have done just that in a bid to improve functioning, rather than backward-focused rating and ranking, a greater emphasis on teams than on individuals looks like the exact opposite of what they are abandoning.

Impacts and Top Recommendations for Rethinking PM in the AI ERA

Increase collaboration and transparency in the workplace requires re-evaluating traditional PMS for more continuous, engaging approaches. Changes in PM practices, such as removing the annual appraisal score, force a rethink of compensation policies, program and tools. Increased performance feedback frequency and gratification will lead to increase usage of individual employee performance metrics. Increased performance feedback frequency and gratification will lead to increase usage of individual employee performance metrics. They are few recommendations for rethinking PM in the AI era as it embraces new approaches in employee PM that support frequent performance conversations, personalized development and visibility of accomplishments. Hire managers with strong coaching and communication skills and hire for and develop digital dexterity across the workforce. Adjust compensation practices to make new performance management alternatives more effective. Re-evaluate practices and policies around data sharing with individuals and teams, balancing the risk of over sharing and under sharing while supporting the need for greater transparency.

The Traditional PM Cycle

Figure: 3 Source: By Michael Armstrong of Performance Management

The first stage of this performance management cycle is planning which was traditionally carried out only once each year. In the first stage employees are set SMART objectives, plan and a review of the employee's job requirements, next stages are 'Act' and 'Track', which occur throughout the year track progress, and provide feedback and the final stage, 'Review', often combining it with employee performance ratings. The 'Review' phase traditionally encompasses an annual performance review, a meeting where employee and manager discuss and evaluate goal progression and completion, performance issues, training and development, and opportunities for advancement. Because of the inadequacies of this annual process, companies around the world have adopted a more agile performance management cycle.

Literature Review on PMS

Stephanie C. Payne, Margaret T. Horner (2008) has compared worker reactions to the usage of a web overall performance appraisal (PA) to the usual paper-and-pencil (P&P) technique. A quasi-experimental study comparing the reactions with a paper and pen performance appraisal instrument to the reactions of employees evaluated with an online model of the same evaluation device. There is a need to provide the software-training program and properly-educate in the way to offer ratings and feedback through the device. The future need to examine manager and human resource (HR) supervisor reactions to the machine learning, additional individual variables, variables related to technology recognition and employers may be more knowledgeable of adopting similar generation in performance appraisal and work to make certain that the high-quality and application of the PA are improved instead of hindered.

Peter Prowse Julie Prowse (2009) assessed methods of appraisal and the difficulties encountered within the appraisal process. The researcher used literature review to evaluate the appraisal system. Further scope is researcher has to investigate an alternative ways of feedback, develop motivation, identify training needs and potential and evidence that can justify potential career development and justify reward.

Anitha J, (2014) viewed various factors that effect employee engagement and focused on the reason that impact relationship among employee overall performance and worker engagement. The random sampling methods and data analysis was carried out using the regression technique, survey questionnaire. The variables recognized were working environment, management, team and co-employee, education and career improvement, reimbursement programme, rules and techniques and workplace wellbeing. In findings working environment, team and peer relationship were found to have significant values in relating with employee engagement and performance of employees. The future scope is for in-depth analysis of factors that effect individual employee engagement and employee performance.

Anastasia A. Katou, (2017) has categorised organisational outcomes into three primary groups HR outcomes such as employee skills, employee attitudes and employee behaviour; operational outcomes such as productivity, growth and creativity; and financial outcomes such as sales growth, return on equity, and return on assets. The researcher aims to assert that HRM sequentially influences the three types of organisational outcomes. Major findings that Business strategies positively influence features and actual HR practices. Researcher could not rule out the possibility correlations between the dependent and independent variables and thus, the study does not allow for dynamic causal inferences. Future research could benefit by using longitudinal research that Investigate the impact of both content and process of HRM systems on Operational performance through employee attitudes and employee behaviour.

Objectives of Study

Primary Objective

- To know the various changes organisations are making to their performance management systems.

Secondary Objective

- To highlight the common critiques of performance management systems.
- To highlight the reasons of companies rethinking performance management.
- To know the future of Performance Management system in artificial intelligence era.

Research Methodology

For achieving the objective of study, conceptual research method has been adopted and case study approach to determine and analysis of data. From a thorough literature review, a gap has

been identified on the area of modern appraisals and critics provided as per the gaps. The analysis is based on primary data collected through focus group interviews of managers performing appraisals and few HR managers. The majority of the analysis is base on secondary data, which is already available and facilitates understanding the recent trends in performance management system. The findings are based on qualitative analysis of the collected information.

Critical Analysis of Performance Management System

As organisations have become increasingly employee-focused and less process-driven. The emphasis has moved from quantity to quality of conversations and feedback as companies of all sizes are shifting away from annual appraisals to more regular ‘check-ins’ and frequent real-time feedback and the redesign of performance management. The PMS aims at providing employees and managers with a framework for having high-quality discussions and giving effective feedback. Performance management frameworks or systems should encourage future-focused, developmental dialogue supported by real-time, qualitative feedback. Decouple performance measurement are striving towards ‘simplicity’, ‘ridiculously easy to understand’, and this is something businesses are now waking up.

New performance management software tools are been rapidly adopted. As organisations are rapidly adopting a new generation of performance management tools such as clear Review software. Such tools enable employees to receive and request feedback in real-time, send automated email reminders to ensure employees and their managers check-in with each other regularly, provide online agendas for effective one-to-one conversations and give HR and senior management visibility of whether regular performance discussions are taking place. These tools also enable agile objectives and shorter-term priorities to be agreed and monitored, as opposed to traditional performance management software, which typically ties organisations into an annual goal setting cycle.

The PMS should be more productive and motivated and there should be PA twice in a year or more.

Figure: 4

Source: Explaining the Stages of the Performance Management Cycle, by Stuart Hearn, Aug 28, 2017, Blog (<https://clearreview.com/stages-of-performance-management-cycle/>)

In this approach employees and managers periodically reviewed at ‘check-in’ meetings, new near-term goals are also agreed and future-focused, action-oriented discussions

Criticism for New Continuous Pm Cycle

Analysis of the step-by-step process of the new continuous Performance management cycle reveals few critical points. The regular one-to-one performance conversations will lead to a time consuming process rendering it inefficient interms of costs involved. Hence, the new continuous

model is expensive. Performance errors such as leniency, favouritism halo effect and stereotype error may take place. Multiple feedbacks may lead to confusion among the employees about the expectation and negative impact on employee’s motivation and productivity. The appraiser should be aware of the performance appraisal variables to evaluate the employees. Feedback can be useless if it is not carefully and smoothly dealt. Finally, requirement of training in order to achieve efficient working of the performance appraisal system and to keep employees motivated and productive, organisations will need to develop trusting and flexible working environments.

Recommended Model

Figure: 5 Recommended model

The Practical Implications

The effectiveness of performance management system (PMS) has been a critical issue for the organizations. Implications of Performance Management is a continuous process that creates a working culture to encourage employees to improve their work performance and reach their full potential during their stay of employment. Performance Management also provides strategic direction, develop competency in employees and organization value. Performance management gives managers and employees more in setting their goals and more accountability for accomplishing them. Meanwhile the appraiser should be clear about the variables of evaluation and give proper feedback to employees. The linking performance and rewards will motivate the employees to be better performers. Performance needs to be evaluated in scheduled intervals, which will help employees to achieve the results. Thus, allowing the organization to spend less time making corrections due to their employees. Prominent Performance Plans the co-systems of the plan work to make sure the goals are achievable. While performance management tools can be processes that are put in place, such as frequent performance discussions and recognition schemes, a performance management tool can also refer to a software package. Performance management software is a performance management tool that can be used to improve company-wide communication, facilitate real-time feedback and schedule one-on-one meetings. Due to software, thousands of employees enjoy more regular and more effective performance conversations with their managers.

Conclusion

The world of Performance management is drastically changing from traditional methods towards more effective, transparent, criteria based and feedback oriented modern methods. The older, database methods of evaluation have proved to be ineffective. Instead, business leaders will employ several different ideas. The companies need forward-looking performance reviews, focusing more on development and coaching and less on assessment. New performance management software tools are rapidly adopted and the companies should know about the software usage. Embrace new approaches in employee performance management that support frequent performance conversations, personalized development and visibility of accomplishments. Employee PM tools help to motivate workforce. Most employees are more motivated by appreciation than money and it can also minimise voluntary turnover. The organisations need to realise the benefits of adopting the recent trends of performance management and work towards organisation goals in SMART way ie; Specific, measurable, achievable, realistic, time fame. Therefore the organisations can achieve set targets by satisfying the employees.

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